

PLEDGE

Politics of Grievance and Democratic Governance

Data Management Plan

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Glossary and Abbreviations	
BibTeX	Bibliographic flat-file database file format and a software program for processing these files to produce lists of references.
CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research
DataCite	DataCite is an international not-for-profit organization which aims to improve data citation.
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier is a standardized unique number given to articles, papers, books to identify a particular publication.
Dublin Core	Standardized metadata set for describing information resources like documents, videos, images, services, and other digital artifacts.
GDPR	The EU general data protection regulation which governs how the personal data of individuals in the EU may be processed and transferred.
MARXML	The MARXML toolkit is a set of Java programs which allow users to convert to and from the MARC file format (including full character set conversion) and other formats available in the MARXML architecture.
Mendeley	A reference manager software.
ROR ID	A Research Organization Registry (ROR) ID is a unique identifier assigned to research organizations, designed to provide a standardized way of referencing these entities across various systems and databases.
OAI- PMH	The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting is a low-barrier mechanism for repository interoperability.
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID is a unique, persistent identifier for researchers and scholars to distinguish their work and affiliations from those of others.
PID	Persistent Identifier is a long-lasting reference to a digital resource or object, ensuring consistent access and citation.
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work package

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Executive Summary

The PLEDGE project has established an initial version of its Data Management Plan (DMP) to ensure comprehensive management of research data generated throughout its duration. This DMP outlines the lifecycle of data collection, usage, storage, archiving, and sharing, with a specific focus on adhering to the EU's open science principles to promote openness, transparency, and accessibility. It will be regularly updated and reviewed to accommodate the project's evolving needs and datasets.

The DMP details the handling of both primary and secondary data within the project.

PLEDGE is committed to the FAIR data management principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Re-usability). Data will be stored and shared using the ZENODO data repository, ensuring long-term accessibility and compliance with open science mandates.

The DMP outlines specific roles and responsibilities for data management. PLEDGE guarantees the ethical processing of personal data, focusing on minimizing risks, ensuring privacy, and preventing unauthorized use. Measures include secure storage, pseudonymization, anonymization, and compliance with GDPR and national regulations.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

This document is the initial version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the PLEDGE project. The definition of research data means any research results generated by the PLEDGE project, excluding personal data. The DMP aims to outline all data collected, used, and generated throughout the project. It details the data lifecycle, covering how data will be stored, archived, shared, and made available via ZENODO <<https://zenodo.org/>> data repository infrastructure. For personal data, the DMP ensures appropriate collection, processing, sharing, archiving, or deletion.

Conceived as a living document, the DMP will be regularly updated and reviewed throughout the project's duration, if necessary. The first version of the DMP is delivered in month 7. The datasets mentioned are currently in draft form, and this initial version of the DMP reflects the current data management plans. Detailed information about datasets will be delivered later, in month 36. The datasets mentioned here are in draft form or still under collection. This initial DMP version represents the current data management plans. Detailed information about datasets will be logged as the PLEDGE project progresses.

Our project is committed to adhering to the EU's open science principles¹ by ensuring that our data management practices facilitate openness, transparency, and accessibility. This Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the strategies we will employ to achieve these goals.

¹ https://rea.ec.europa.eu/open-science_en

1.2 Summary of secondary data use

PLEDGE involves secondary data which are summarized in the Catalogue of Consortium Database:

Name of the dataset	Provider	Data Type	Main topics
Social Cohesion	Interaction In Civil Society	Non-probability Quota Sampled Survey data	Civic engagement, Issue Cleavage Identification, Intergroup Emotion, Immigration, Climate Housing Issue
SolZiv	Interaction In Civil Society	Non-probability Quota Sampled Survey data	Civic engagement, PANAS, grievance as targets/objects of emotions (policies, economy, health, others' behaviour), intergroup emotions, perceived emotional synchrony, personality (Big 5), political attitudes
Manifesting guilt and shame in the election campaign of 2022 Hungary	HUN-REN Centre for Social Sciences	Collection of social media content (political leaders) and online news media outlet; annotated data	Political use of emotions in rhetoric and news media coverage
Youth Radicalism in Europe: Islamophobia	Ayhan Kaya (Grant Agreement: 785934, ERC Advanced Grant)	Interview transcriptions in English	Radicalism, populism, Islamism, Islamophobia, nativism, socioeconomic deprivation, nostalgia
Psyched up for party reforms	Thomas Legein/EDGE program (VUB)	Experimental data	Personality traits, Moral foundations, Emotions
Polarization Tracker	Political Psychology Lab (University of Cambridge)/MHP Group	Non-probability Quota Sampled Survey data	Affective polarization, Moral foundations, Intergroup emotions, Misinformation, Trust in (political) actors
Polarisation in Turkey - Dimensions of Polarization in	Emre Erdoğan	Survey	Social identities, party preferences, and alignments, polarization.

Turkey (2015-2017-2020)			
Effective Struggle with Infodemic (2020)	Emre Erdoğan and Pinar Uyan-Semerçi	Survey and Interviews	COVID-19 and misinformation
Religion and emotions among the far right	Aletta Diefenbach / Affective Societies / FU Berlin	Group Discussions	Religion and emotional boundary-making
EoS RepResent Longitudinal Survey	EoS RepResent consortium (FWO/FNRS)	Non-probability Quota Sampled Survey data	Trust in (political) actors; Issue Cleavage Identification; Feeling represented; democratic reforms; Intergroup Emotion
EOS RepResent Focus Group Dataset	EoS RepResent consortium (FWO/FNRS)	Focus group transcripts	Civic engagement; Issue Cleavage Identification; Immigration; Climate; Housing issue; Emotions; Trust in (political) actors
Values in Crisis Survey (first wave)	National Centre for Social Research	Quantitative Study with Data -Non-probability: Quota	COVID-19, values, social change
Collective Action of Indignant Citizens in Greece: First & Second Wave	University of Macedonia	Quantitative Data	Political participation, political attitudes, social values, minorities, gender, LGBTQA+, and refugees.
Political & Social Radicalism in Greece.	University of Macedonia	Quantitative Data	Political participation, social values, economy
What Greek people believe -2020	διαΝΕΟσις	Quantitative Data	Social issues, Public policy, demography. Migration; Economic conditions; Social change; Social conditions and indicators
EOSNotLikeUs Focus Group Dataset	EoS NotLikeUs consortium (FWO/FNRS)	Focus group transcripts	Issue Cleavage Identification; Intergroup Emotion; Emotions; Trust in (political) actors; Feeling represented
METRON FORUM 2.0	METRON ANALYSIS	Non-probability Quota Sampled Survey data	Social trust, political trust, right or wrong direction of the country's course, economic trust index
METRON FORUM 2.0	METRON ANALYSIS	Non-probability Quota Sampled Survey data	Right or wrong direction of the country's course, immigration and pandemic as important problems

An Insight into the Minds of Voters	Eteron - Institute for Research and social Change	Online panel (3681) and non-probability Quota sampling (CATI - 501)	Political trust, (dis)satisfaction with democracy, radicalism, immigration, preference of dictatorship over democracy, feelings, social trust
European Social Survey 2nd Round Greece -ESS2 GR	OPINION-National Centre for Social Research	Probability sampled, face to face interviews	Trust, social values, social exclusion, health, work, well-being
check4facts- Attitudes and Perceptions of Public Information in Greece	National Centre for Social Research- University of Athens Media Dpt Social Research Lab on Media	Quantitative Study with Data -Non-probability- Web based structured questionnaire	Fact-checking of four pillars: health; immigration; climate change; criminality
EP 2019 Twitter dataset	University of Helsinki	Twitter database, categorized accounts, topic-modelled data	EP campaigns and social media

Table 1 Summary of secondary data focusing on emotions, grievances, and social sharing.

In addition, European Social Survey R6; World Value Survey; National Election Studies (e.g. German Longitudinal Election Study 2000 onwards); Eurobarometer; European Value Survey; VDem; International Social Survey Programme on emotion-specific measures such as well-being, resentment, emotions towards political issues and variables like issue evaluations, trust, values, life satisfaction, orientations towards democracy, media consumption, political participation, identities, and group attachments will be including.

The purpose of reusing the existing dataset is to:

- assess and delineate the consortium's research contributions;
- gain insights into current concepts and methodologies, including their limitations;
- map the field and identify potential stakeholders;

- conduct a multi-level analysis of the data;
- examine and critically evaluate competing definitions, concepts, and theories in social sciences related to grievance politics and policymaking.

1.3 Summary of primary data use

PLEDGE primary data includes:

(1) National 3-wave longitudinal surveys across the consortium. Nationally representative samples, 600 participants per wave. The research will be registered on an open research repository and the aggregate level data will be made publicly available upon publication.

(2) Lab experiments: Experiment 1. restricts sharing of grievances, Experiment 2. infuses positive emotionality into EMRes, Experiment 3. stimulates strong ingroup ties as opposed to other forms of identification. Experiment 1 is a 3 (envy, shame, helpless anger) x 3 (control, sharing, sharing restriction) between subjects sequential design; Experiment 2 is a between subjects factorial design with 12 conditions: 3 negative emotions (envy, shame, helpless anger) x 4 positive emotion manipulations (gratitude, joy, pride, control); Experiment 3 a two-condition experiment varying victimhood through trauma reminders.

(3) Qualitative interviews with Interview Set 1 (IS1): 30 elected and appointed policy actors; IS2: 30 government officials and civil servants who generate policies to access their practices; IS3: 3 Foreign policy experts on how emotions shape the reactions of European states; IS4: 30 interviews with citizens on how they engage with emotions; IS5: interviews with 20 female leaders on gender and emotions in grievance politics.

(4) Focus groups: Examine the affective features of grievance politics in group interactions and their practices, including feeling and display rules, dominant emotion regulation strategies, and their preferred modes of collective action. Explore the dynamics of identity-driven grievances across peaceful and war contexts among previously aggrieved groups and

test potential reactions to various policy measures aimed at integrating these groups. In-depth analysis of the Russo-Ukrainian war (focus group in Latvia with Russian speaking minority) and climate/energy activists.

(5) Social Media Data: Data collection 4 weeks around EP2024: grievance messages and the virality of anti/pro-democratic grievances in the most popular networking platforms (e.g., Instagram, Tiktok, and Youtube): (3.4.1) a) design and extract Internet data using digital methods; and b) develop framework of guidelines for qualitative and quantitative content analysis in a comparative setting, combining text mining and data mining tools, web scraping techniques, sampling, identifying relevant social media platforms for cross-country comparison. The PLEDGE social media database will be constructed by hashtag and keyword filtering of parties, leaders, EU officials, MEP candidates, relevant social movements, across multiple platforms, following GDPR, during May 2024 for EP. As audiovisual data is an emotional form of communication, we will use methods available in 2024 to extract this data. This data gathering and processing is done in collaboration with ENDURE, CO3 and MORES, where the lead is from UH as also background pilots for the data gathering effort. Data sharing between the members of sibling projects is possible, as long as PLEDGE receives the relevant data for the WP 3-5 needs (3.4.1-2; 4.3.1; 5.1.1-2, 5.2.1, 5.3.1-2). Social media content will not be shared publicly, however, aggregated and anonymized data will be made publicly available.

(6) Traditional Media data: Data collection on the news media coverage of grievance politics with traditional media sample for cross-country comparison. News media content will not be shared publicly, however, aggregated and anonymized data will be made publicly available.

(7) VR content from Poland and Ukraine. Qualitative content and narrative analysis and review of techniques used in immersive VR where there is no direct interaction with human subjects content to regulate users' emotions and perspective-taking, affective polarization, democratic listening, and participation. VR content will not be shared publicly, however, aggregated and anonymized data will be made publicly available.

(8) Peer research (citizen science approach, 10 persons), whereby non-professional researchers are trained and enabled to collaborate in the research endeavour. Peer-research includes elements of peer-support, in which those involved draw on peer and personal networks and experience to support each other and collect and transfer knowledge.

Specific information on the primary dataset (incl. a short description of the data, types of the generated/collected data, formats, size, and contact persons) is provided in Section 5.

In 2, 3, 4, 7 and 8 data are collected and stored using digital audio recording devices with the permission of the participants. Interviewers should utilize reliable and secure devices for recording interviews, such as digital audio recorders or encrypted applications. Recordings should be promptly backed up to secure locations. Once the recordings are safely uploaded, the files should be deleted from the recording devices. When respondents did not wish to be recorded, interviews and focus groups were undertaken in pairs to enable detailed note-taking. The necessary documents were prepared prior to fieldwork, including a letter with information about the project, anonymity, confidentiality, data sharing, and informed consent (translate into the languages which will be used for the experiments, interviews and focus groups). To ensure that the content is understood, the informed consent form will be explained in writing and verbally before starting the activity. The PLEDGE data will be utilized primarily by the scientific community, but can be also useful for our further target groups: governmental bodies (policy makers on the EU and the national level); affected professional communities (journalists, teachers, students); and the civil society (NGOs, think tanks, foundations) as well as the general public. Data sharing is permitted only when the dataset is anonymized and aggregated.

PLEDGE guarantees fair and transparent processing of personal data, taking into account the specific circumstances and context in which the data are processed by appropriate technical and organizational measures.

These measures aim to:

- minimize the risk of errors including data loss;
- avoid any potential risks to the human subjects involved in the proposed research activities and ensure their privacy;
- prevent unauthorized use of data which might lead to discriminatory actions based on racial or ethnic origin, political opinion, religion or beliefs, trade union membership, genetic or health status, or sexual orientation.

2. FAIR data

PLEDGE is committed to the Open Science principle and will handle data according to the FAIR data management principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Re-usability). PLEDGE researchers aim to amplify the access to and re-use of the research data they will generate. However, certain datasets or parts of datasets cannot be shared to protect the privacy of voluntary participants in data collection procedures.

The data in PLEDGE consists of raw data, processed data, and metadata. Generally, the raw and small-scale processed data are made available for the PLEDGE researchers, who are working on the analysis, in PLEDGE's MS TEAMS platform excluding personal data. Data that may include sensitive information, for example, the experiment, focus groups, and interview data can be stored with activity leaders and partners' secure and password-protected platforms, particularly in the processing period. Personal data might be linked to surveys, as these instruments are intended to be used as one of the sources for focus groups and experiments.

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

As a general rule, PLEDGE will allow third parties to find datasets free of charge for any user for research purposes, governed by Creative Commons licenses. PLEDGE will utilize Creative Commons (CC) licenses to grant copyright permissions for creative works. As a general rule, PLEDGE considers the CC-BY-SA license. This license allows others to remix, tweak, and build upon the work of PLEDGE participants, provided they credit the original work and license their new creations under identical terms. Consequently, any new work based on our data and results will carry the same license. When necessary, the project will use less restrictive licenses, such as CC-BY, or more restrictive licenses, such as CC-BY-NC. The CC-BY is a Creative Commons Attribution license that permits re-distribution and re-use of a licensed work, provided that proper credit is given to the creator. The Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial (CC-BY-NC) license allows others to re-distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon a licensed work non-commercially, as long as they credit the creator. However, the use of the material for commercial purposes is not included. The licenses will be determined by the Activity leaders and the Data Protection Officer. The Consortium leader and the Work package leader might be involved in the decision-making.

The public data can also remain reusable via ZENODO for at least 20 years. ZENODO is an open repository maintained by CERN, where datasets, documents, and other research materials can be found via the ZENODO search engine. The host laboratory CERN currently states that

the lifetime period is 20 years. In the event that ZENODO has to close its operations, CERN has to migrate all content (including metadata) to other suitable repositories.

Persistent identifiers (PIDs) are key in ensuring the findability of research outputs, including research data. PIDs will be provided for the dataset (such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) or a handle), for all author(s) involved in the action (such as ORCIDs or ResearcherIDs) and, if possible, for their organisations (such as ROR IDs) and the grant (such as grant IDs).

To make the data findable PLEDGE researchers will implement specific data naming conventions and versioning principles as follows:

- PLEDGE uses standard naming conventions, including the following components: [activity number] _ [partner institution] _ [document type] _ [version number] _ [date (YYYYMMDD)];
- Researchers are requested to add any other important metadata that will help identifying files and data (e.g. country identifier if relevant) in between [document type] and [version number];
- For example:

3.4.1_CSS_TikTokdatabase_cleansed_HU_v1.4_20251104

or

3.3.1_ULUND_interview transcript_policymakers_anonymised_BE_v2.0_20251104

Versioning should be followed by the following guideline:

- filename with v1 indicates that it is a first version of any research documentation;
- v1.x indicates that the file is an updated version of v1 in the case of small modifications made to any of the previous versions (e.g. grammatically checked and corrected interview transcripts; database with formally checked and corrected headings, typos, grammar, etc.);
- v2 indicates that the file is a significantly updated version of v1 (e.g. cleansed database; anonymised interview transcript);
- FINAL indicates that the file is considered the last version of the document.

2.2 Making data accessible

Data share within the PLEDGE consortium

At the consortium level, the Activity leaders decide on the limitation of data sharing with the other PLEDGE researchers, if they are confidential or sensitive, in agreement with the Consortium and Work package leaders, after consulting the Data Protection Officer and the Ethics Officer of the project. The consortium's external partners who may have been involved in data gathering can also access the data before submitting the dataset to ZENODO. External partners may gain researcher or team leader-level access to data. Personal data will be restricted and accessible to PLEDGE researchers involved in the specific activity (interviews, focus groups, experiments) only. Sensitive, confidential, and personal data, for which PLEDGE researchers have received consent, will be stored and managed as the Ethics Review of the activity declares.

Data share with third parties

All processed, structured, and pseudonymized or anonymized data will be made available through the trusted repository of the ZENODO <<https://zenodo.org/>>. Registration is requested for using ZENODO. Researchers from any discipline can upload data in any file format. ZENODO complies with the data management requirements of Horizon Europe, the ERC, and other EU research and innovation funding programs. CERN possesses the technical expertise to supply the infrastructure.

Metadata associated with each published dataset in ZENODO will include:

- abstract/description;
- access and licensing information;
- associated projects;
- associated publications and reports;
- bibliographic information;
- changelogs;

- contact details;
- Digital Object Identifiers (DOI);
- grant information;
- keywords;
- language;
- and version numbers.

Additional information can be included as metadata, such as a disclaimer.

ZENODO allows PLEDGE to harvest the entire repository via the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI- PMH).

PLEDGE imposes a year-long embargo on the data. As a general rule, the consortium grants external access to the data collection 12 months after the final dataset is submitted to ZENODO. Activity leaders may propose a shorter embargo period, and Bilateral Research Data Sharing Agreements between sister projects may also have different terms.

PLEDGE is dedicated to collaboration with sister projects. While there is no universal definition of a sister project, it typically refers to another EU-funded initiative that addresses the same topic as PLEDGE and aims to solve similar problems while contributing to the calls' expected outcomes. A key aspect of this collaboration is data sharing, which must be mutually agreed upon and beneficial. To ensure the security, integrity, and proper management of its research data, PLEDGE restricts data access to authorized users, uses data solely for agreed-upon purposes, refrains from disclosing data to third parties without prior approval, and securely stores and responsibly disposes of all data. The data sharing process will be governed by a Research Data Sharing Agreement, signed by the leaders of the participating projects. The initial template for the agreement will be provided in Annex 1. The agreement has to be approved by the Coordinator's Legal Services.

2.3 Making data interoperable

The produced data of the PLEDGE project must be interoperable. Interoperability can be realized both at the dataset metadata level and at the data level. As for the metadata, ZENODO uses JSON schema as the internal representation of metadata and offers the option to export to other formats such as Dublin Core, MARCXML, BibTeX, CSL, DataCite, and Mendeley.

If possible, the same dataset will be distributed in different forms: xlsx file – csv file; word – txt – pdf, etc.

PLEDGE will consider the use of terms what are similar to other researchers use when searching for literature and databases.

PLEDGE will prioritize in the data description:

- key phrases that comprise two, or three words (instead of single words which may be too general);
- key phrases that are not presented in the database's title;
- key phrases that are significant abbreviations, and acronyms in our field.

2.4 Increase data re-use

The metadata and sources for the open dataset will be available on PLEDGE's website <<https://www.pledgeproject.eu/>>. The news about the data sharing will also be disseminated through PLEDGE's social media channels and relevant events.

The readme file will be deposited. The so-called readme files summarise the circumstances of the research and the most important information (brief description of the research, methodology, content of the data set, description of the files, etc.) to make the research data and documentation understandable and reusable. The readme file can be either an outline or a coherent text document and can be based on any description of the research (e.g. research design, codebook, sampling, field notes, list of sources, code, algorithms, scripts, protocols).

3. Allocation of resources and responsibilities

Persons responsible for Research Data Management in the PLEDGE project:

- Activity leaders see section 5;
- Data Protection Officer (DPO): Tomi Toivio, University of Helsinki;
- Work package leader: Gabriella Szabó, HUN REN Centre for Social Sciences;

- Consortium leader: Emilia Palonen, University of Helsinki and Mikko Salmela, University of Helsinki.

The activity leaders and partners, who are involved in collecting sensitive data, are responsible for storing personal data during, and after the end of the research. In non-EU countries, personal data must be stored in compliance with the national and/or institutional regulations after the end of the project. Data repositories should guarantee to migrate all project content (including metadata) to other suitable repositories in the event that they must cease operations.

PLEDGE partners are responsible for data security as well. Researchers should not carry personal data on pendrives, flash drives, external hard drives, or save it in other cloud applications such as Google Drive or Dropbox. If data is lost, inadvertently disclosed, accessed by unauthorized persons, altered, or becomes unavailable, partners should notify the Activity leaders, WP leaders, and the Project Coordinator. The WP leader should register such incidents, and in certain cases, notify the Consortium leader and concerned authority and/or the data subjects in some extreme and serious cases.

All beneficiaries of PLEDGE will undertake the responsibility to follow the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 (General Data Protection Regulation, hereinafter GDPR). Beneficiary from a third country has been required to ensure that all relevant provisions in the GDPR shall be applied and provide appropriate safeguards and that enforceable data subject rights and effective legal remedies for data subjects are available. The definition of personal data used by this document is identical to the definition used by GDPR.

Each Activity leader is responsible for ensuring that the Activity's data collection will be in accordance with the Data Management Plan. Activity leaders, the Data Protection Officer, and the WP leader should collaborate to submit the datasets to ZENODO.

4. Ethics

Data collection activities of interviews, surveys, focus groups, and experiments will be designed to ensure privacy. Personal data will only be requested when necessary for research purposes.

The data subjects are informed of the existence of research profiling, if possible consequences, and how their fundamental rights are safeguarded. Vulnerable groups (such as LGBTQIA+, ethnic minorities, and migrant participants, etc.) are identified via national and local experts, NGOs and associations. Experiments, focus group participation and interviews will be anonymized. The storage of any personal data complies with the GDPR regulations.

PLEDGE will respect individuals involved in research by recognizing their autonomy to make independent decisions free from external pressures. Participants should be able to make an informed decision about whether to participate in research based on comprehensive written information provided through the informed consent process. If needed, further clarification will be provided verbally. In other words, individuals can only participate in PLEDGE research voluntarily.

Researchers secure in advance the consent of the persons who will participate in the research or their guardians and legal representatives. According to the national and European legislation, researchers will fully ensure the protection of the participants' personal data. This is done through the privacy notice at the project and partner websites, as well as raising awareness of the data in public.

Personal data are stored exclusively on the password-protected server system of the Activity leaders and partners accessible only for particular partner researchers working on the PLEDGE project with the specific tasks related to the data. Different levels of accessibility are applied: in order to enhance awareness on privacy and data security issues, the Activity leader and the Data Protection Officer grant access to sensitive data to researchers that may be WP leaders and relevant task leaders who have received a privacy and data management awareness training, provided by the Work package and Consortium leaders.

5. Activity level- data management specifications

Activity 3.2.1: Longitudinal survey

Short info.	Types of the generated/ collected data	Formats of the described generated/ collected data	Expected data size	Ethics	People that will be responsible for the management of the described data and ethics	Contact address
Longitudinal survey (3 waves) conducted in 11 countries	Database of participants' responses to the set of closed-ended questions	Data: .sav, .csv Questionnaire: .docx and .pdf	Max. 50 MB	Data will be anonymous, there will be an ethical review of the entire questionnaire and survey procedure.	Michał Bilewicz, Maciej Siemiątkowski	bilewicz@psych.uw.edu.pl ; maciej.siemiatkowski@psych.uw.edu.pl

Table 2 Summary of Longitudinal survey data.

Activity 3.2.2: Experiments

Short info.	Types of the generated/collected data	Formats of the described generated/collected data	Expected data size	Ethics	People that will be responsible for the management of the described data and ethics	Contact address
Experimental studies that will be focused on: 1) restricting the sharing of grievances, 2) infusing positive emotionality into EMRes, 3) stimulating strong ingroup ties as opposed to other forms of identification.	After anonymization, database of the answers given by the participants to the set of questions and numeric values indicating the emotions identified by the facial recording procedure.	Data: .sav, .csv Questionnaire: .docx, pdf	30 MB	Ethical review of the entire procedure of each of the experiments, as well as all the questions that will be included, with a special focus on the facial recording procedure. These recordings will not be made	Tereza Capelos, Michał Bilewicz, Maciej Siemiątkowski	T.Capelos@soton.ac.uk, maciej.siemiakowski@psych.uw.edu.pl, bilewicz@psych.uw.edu.pl

				available, only the numerical values indicating the identified emotions will be shared.		
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Table 3 Summary of Experiment data.

Activity 3.3.2: Focus groups

Short info.	Types of the generated/collected data	Formats of the described generated/collected data	Expected data size	Ethics	People that will be responsible for the management of the described data and ethics	Contact address
Focus groups with activists and voters	Transcribed text, field notes and audio records using agreed formats and standards for handling the issue of multiple voices, interruptions,	Word, pdf, .wav, mp4	8 GB	Sensitive data, ethics review is necessary	Gavin Sullivan	gavin.sullivan@ipu-berlin.de

	labelling of participatory and visual activities.					
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Table 4 Summary of Focus group data.

Activity 3.3 Interviews in activities 3.3.3 and 3.3.4

Short info.	Types of the generated/collected data	Formats of the described generated/collected data	Expected data size	Ethics	People that will be responsible for the management of the described data and ethics	Contact address
Interviews with policy makers, activists, academics	Audiofiles and transcripts	Word, pdf, .wav, mp4	5 GB	Ethics review is needed. Sensitive data and non-sensitive data, anonymization is necessary	Ian Manners; Dolors Palau-Sampio; Gavin Sullivan; Karen Celis; Thomas Legin; Emilia Palonen; Kanerva Kuokkanen	ian.manners@svet.lu.se ; dolors.palau@uv.es; gavin.sullivan@ipu-berlin.de karen.celis@vub ; thomas.legein@vub.be ; hepp@helsinki.fi

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Table 5 Summary of Interview data.

Activity 3.4.1: Social Media Analysis

Short info.	Types of the generated/collected data	Formats of the described generated/collected data	Expected data size	Ethics	People that will be responsible for the management of the described data and ethics	Contact address
Instagram, YouTube, TikTok videos, video thumbnails and metadata of videos. Screen recording and research	1) Video and image files 2) Metadata of videos in SQL/CSV format. 3) Pre-analysis of the large data set in	SQL, CSV, MP4, JPG.	2TB scraped data files, 2 TB screen recording files that are co-ordinated to a common	Ethics check at the University of Helsinki on 17 April. Data includes personal identifiers	Emilia Palonen, Tomi Toivio	Hepp@helsinki.fi, emilia.palonen@helsinki.fi; tomi.toivio@helsinki.fi

<p>notes from Instagram and TikTok from 10 countries by 3 data gatherers (circa 1 hour of coverage per day). Period of analysis 20/5-16/6/2024.</p>	<p>workbooks, visuals representations or other</p>		<p>dataset</p>	<p>(name) and political views expressed in the public domain. The data is available for research use following the EU copyright act and can only be shared for research use. Aggregate level data may be shareable</p>		
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Table 6 Summary of Social media data.

For this activity, we have an extensive Data Management Plan as the activity is done in collaboration with several research consortia. The data is stored at the University of Helsinki and the Finnish CSC data storage, where it is accessed by partners. The ethics check for the research has been conducted and passed at the University of Helsinki for the data gathering.

Activity 3.4.2: Study of Traditional Media

Short info	Types of the generated/ collected data	Formats of the described generated/collected data	Expected data size	Ethics	People that will be responsible for the management of the described data and ethics	Contact address
Articles	Pdfs, excel document with database links	Pdf, word, excel	<1G	Subject to copyright and subscription	N. Demertzis, D. Palau-Sampio	ndemert@media.uoa.gr; dolors.palau@uv.es

Table 7 Summary of Traditional media data.

Activity 3.4.3: Immersive Media and Future Scenarios

Short info.	Types of the generated/collected data	Formats of the described generated/c ollected data	Expected data size	Ethics	People that will be responsible for the management of the described data and ethics	Contact address
Publicly available non-fiction VR/360 video content (apps, games, and films) from government-funded programmes and initiatives in Poland and Ukraine, with a focus on either historical grievances (Poland) or the Russo-Ukrainian war (Ukraine).	Notes on the video files, which includes titles, release dates, sources (where the content can be accessed), creators/producers, language, target audience, content duration, type (educational, documentary, entertainment), and a brief description of each piece's thematic focus.	Immersive video files and notes on the videos.	>1 GB since only written notes on the video items will be shared.	The research does not require ethics review and approval.	Ruta Kazlauskaite	ruta.kazlauskaite@helsinki.fi

Table 8 Summary of Immersive Media content data.

6. Conclusions

The PLEDGE project's Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the processes for managing research data generated, used, and collected throughout the project. This initial version of the DMP, delivered in month 7, is a living document that will be regularly updated to reflect ongoing data management practices. The DMP ensures adherence to the EU's open science principles, emphasizing transparency, accessibility, and the protection of personal data.

The DMP covers the entire data lifecycle, detailing how data will be stored, archived, shared, and made available via the ZENODO data repository. The DMP ensures that personal data is appropriately collected, processed, shared, archived, or deleted in compliance with relevant regulations.

PLEDGE involves secondary data from various sources, summarized in the Catalogue of Consortium Database. This includes datasets on social cohesion, civic engagement, political attitudes, emotional responses, radicalism, and misinformation, among others. The purpose of reusing these datasets is to assess research contributions, gain insights into current concepts and methodologies, map the field, and conduct multi-level analyses.

Primary data in PLEDGE includes:

1. National Longitudinal Surveys: Three-wave surveys with nationally representative samples, made publicly available upon publication.
2. Lab Experiments: Several experiments exploring emotional and social responses under different conditions.
3. Qualitative Interviews: Multiple interview sets with policy actors, government officials, foreign policy experts, citizens, and female leaders.
4. Focus Groups: Studying the affective features of grievance politics, with specific focus groups on the Russo-Ukrainian war and climate/energy activism.
5. Social Media Data: Notes and analyses of grievance messages and the virality of anti/pro-democratic grievances across popular platforms like Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube.
6. Traditional Media Data: Notes and cross-country comparison of news media coverage on grievance politics.
7. VR Content: Notes and qualitative content analysis of immersive VR in Poland and Ukraine.
8. Peer Research: Training non-professional researchers to collaborate in the research process.

Data from these activities are collected using digital audio recording devices, with participant consent ensured through detailed informed consent procedures.

PLEDGE guarantees fair and transparent processing of personal data, implementing measures to minimize errors, protect participant privacy, and prevent unauthorized data use. The project adheres to the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) to ensure open access and reusability of research data. Data within the PLEDGE consortium is shared based on the level of confidentiality and sensitivity, as decided by activity leaders in consultation with ethics and data protection officers. Processed, structured, and pseudonymized/anonymized data will be made available through the ZENODO repository. The project imposes a year-long embargo on data to ensure controlled access, with provisions for earlier sharing under specific agreements. PLEDGE ensures data interoperability at both metadata and data levels, using standardized naming conventions and versioning principles. The data description prioritizes key phrases and acronyms relevant to the field. The project also encourages data reuse by providing detailed metadata and documentation, making data findable and understandable.

Responsibility for data management within PLEDGE lies with activity leaders, the Data Protection Officer (DPO), work package leaders, and consortium leaders. These individuals ensure that data management practices comply with both EU and national regulations, guaranteeing secure storage and responsible handling of personal data.

Overall, the PLEDGE project's DMP sets a robust framework for managing research data, promoting openness and transparency while safeguarding participant privacy and data integrity.

Annexes

Annex 1: Data Sharing Agreement - Template

The Agreement should comply with the following template:

AGREEMENT DETAILS

1. Agreement timeframe

When will this agreement start and end?

Start date:

End date:

2. Research project

Provide a name and a short description of the research project that will use this data

Project name:

Project description:

Research Institution/University:

3. Data users

Who will have access to / use the data?

Name:

Contact details:

Affiliation:

Name:

Contact details:

Affiliation:

4. Details of the data to be shared

Which data will be shared?

Title of dataset / data collection:

Time period the data refers to:

Type(s) of data to be shared:

File format(s) of data to be shared:

(Approx.) Size of data to be shared:

5. Method of access

By what methods will the data be made available to the requester?

Platform of data sharing (e.g. institutional cloud infrastructure):

Method of granting access to data (e.g. online or offline):

6. Support for the data sharing

Who will be supporting the data sharing process?

Name:

Contact details:

6. Purpose of the data sharing

For what purpose is the data being shared?

Research project:

Publication:

Data analysis (type, purpose, entities involved):

7. Permitted use of the data

What are the acceptable uses of the data?

Any restrictions on use (e.g. commercial restriction):

Allowed processing or analyses:

Prohibited processing or analyses:

Current (legal) restrictions that apply to the data:

Restrictions on the disclosure of the data, or information about the data, to third parties by the requester:

8. Sensitivity of the data

Are there any sensitive or personal data being shared?

Any risks that are present in the data:

How they should be managed:

9. Data security

What measures are being taken to ensure data security?

Data storage specifications:

Access control:

Analysis environments:

Transfer of the data:

10. Derived data

What are the specifications of the derived data?

Ownership:

Any restrictions on any of the datasets derived from the shared data:

11. Research outputs

Are there any requests or restrictions regarding the shared data by the provider?

Restrictions on the outputs of the project:

Request to review outputs before they are made public:

12. Retention and disposal of the data

What are the requirements for how the data must be handled after the end of the project?

Retention of the data:

Disposal of the data:

13. References

What does the provider agree to regarding references to the original dataset after it is provided to the requester?

The request(s) of the data provider: Please cite the PLEDGE project (funded by the EU under the Grant Agreement XXXX) as the distributor of the data, the title of the original dataset and data collector (institution(s)). If you encounter any personal data, it is strictly prohibited to publish them.

14. Costs associated with the data sharing

What are the costs associated with the data sharing?

Cost of sharing (infrastructure-related):

Cost of personnel working on sharing the data:

Who is responsible for meeting any costs associated with sharing the data:

15. Signoff for the DSA

What are the details of those who signed off on the agreement?

Name:

Contact details:

Name:

Contact details:

Name:

Contact details:

Input from the legal and research office or equivalent to ensure compliance (official number of document):

Date of the agreement or document